

OPTIMIZATION APPROACH FOR THE CURING PROCESS OF EPOXY MATRIX COMPOSITES USING BOTH THERMAL & MICROWAVE ENERGY

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SUMMARY: Microwave curing of polymer matrix composites has proven to be an attractive substitute for conventional thermal curing. Industrial applications are currently developed including among others: telecommunications, aerospace, scientific instruments, environmental monitoring, polymers curing, and composites manufacturing. Common research objectives include homogeneity of the cure, the acceleration of cure kinetics, cure reaction mechanism, numerical modeling, and enhancement of mechanical properties. In order to efficiently utilize this form of energy, precise control over power, temperature, and time are applied to achieve set goals: reduce cure time, prevent thermal overshoots, assure complete cure, and maximize mechanical properties. This paper discusses an optimization scenario to achieve these set goals by combining data from calorimetric analysis, insitu temperature and power monitoring, and energy conservation studies.

KEYWORDS: Microwave curing, Optimization, Mechanical properties, Cure kinetics.

INTRODUCTION

High-performance polymeric composites, reinforced with carbon, glass, or aramid fibers, have been effectively used by the aerospace and electronics industries in applications requiring light weight, high specific strength and stiffness, and tailorable thermal-expansion coefficients. The dielectric properties of resin matrix & fibers have made it possible for developing microwave based technologies in printed circuit boards, aviation, and marine fields. However, the hindrance behind the spread and scale up of these applications was mainly the high cost and time of fiber orientation and curing. This is shown in the rapid need for automated forming techniques to assure compaction and defect free products. Microwave, processing, however, have provided feasible solutions for several forming processes.

One example of a practical application of this technology is based on the work by Lind et al [1]. Thermoplastic polymer, PEEK, reinforced with carbon fiber was successfully prepared using single-mode applicator. PEEK is a high performance, semicrystalline thermoplastic polymer which is usually difficult to heat as being semi transparent to microwave fields at room temperatures. When a critical temperature is reached molecular mobility is increased and permanent dipoles start to form which makes it microwave heatable [2]. Enough power was absorbed to rapidly heat the PEEK matrix to melt temperatures so that it could be bonded to a consolidated laminate.

Furthermore, microwave energy has been found to be a feasible, economic source for composites manufacturing during pultrusion process. Polymeric composite pre-form is pulled

through a heated die, where the shape is molded and the matrix cured. The advantage of using microwave energy lies in the feature of direct energy transfer. Instead of using a processing chamber consisting of a quite long heated die due to the slow heat transfer to the polymer matrix and relatively long cure times, a single-mode resonance cavity has been used to rapidly heat the part using microwave radiation in a significantly shorter process chamber, resulting in less force required to pull the fiber bundle through the die [3-6]. The control process is relatively easier than other forming processes due to the mass production nature of the process and the fixed part configuration in each batch.

One of the significant challenges in composites is the processing of thick cross-section parts, one inch or more. The conventional processing, oven based, would require complex cure schedule with very slow thermal ramp rates and isothermal holds to control overheating due to cure reaction exotherm and poor thermal conductivity. The earliest attempt for applying microwave technology for thick sections was the work of Lee and Springer [7]. Not only did they carry out the first curing experiments, but they also developed fundamental electromagnetic models for microwave-material interaction. They also proved the feasibility of curing composites of non-conductive fillers, such as fiberglass, in wave-guide applicators. For conducting carbon fibers, however, they claimed that curing would be limited to unidirectional composites with less than about 32 plies (approximately 7-8 mm thick) due to the high reflectivity of the fibers and, hence, poor penetration depth of the radiation into the composite. Recently, Thostenson and Chou [1,8] further analyzed Lee work by stating that this limitation was due to the high dielectric loss of the carbon fiber. In angle ply laminates, the reflectance of the first few layers was too high to achieve efficient heating of thick laminates. In addition, the incorporation of high conductivity fibers may result in the formation of local hot spots and electrical arcing. Recently, such problem has been eliminated, using a single-mode microwave cavity.

Shull et al. [9] tackled the issue of material degradation as a result of exothermic reactions of cure. Temperature distribution was obtained during microwave processing from a series of thermocouples embedded at various lateral locations relative to the microwave source and uniformly through the thickness of the composite structure. By careful monitoring of the rapid changes in temperatures through the thickness of the material, more control over thermal runaway and large heat exotherm is achieved.

Zhou and Hawley [10] reported the use of what is called "Part Shaped Microwave Cavity". Instead of using a conventional microwave mold made from "transparent" materials, such as Teflon, quartz, or pure polyethylene, the microwave cavity has been designed to be the resonance cavity and the casting mold at the same time. This modification has found feasible application in some liquid composite molding processes, such as resin transfer molding (RTM). The main reason behind this modification is that the mold materials do not possess the mechanical properties to maintain integrity for any cyclic RTM process using pressure. A rectangular brass part-shaped cavity was designed instead to withstand high injection pressures while maintaining structural integrity.

It is clear that in order to improve the properties of glass reinforced composites, it is important to improve and understand the behavior of the thermoset resin itself. Main reason for that is the low dielectric property of glass fibers on the contrary of carbon fibers. Second, although thermoplastics and some thermoset resin like polyester and vinyl ester have also been investigated, most of the efforts are dedicated to DGEBA epoxy resin. This is due to the fact that long time required in thermal curing curbs the spreading of this type of resin. An efficient less time consuming method has to be developed in addition to the design of more process control systems and efficient microwave applicators, which could provide more resources on the cure cycle monitoring and control.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

The resin chosen is a modified Diglycidyl of Bisphenol A (DGEBA) resin. The resin is supplied from Dow Chemicals as DER324 and used as received. The commercial resin in itself is a formulated blend of DER331 (DGEBA) and a reactive diluent C₁₂-C₁₄ aliphatic glycidyl with a blend ratio of 83/17 respectively. In order to reach optimum properties, a curing agent must be used to build a three dimensional, thermoset network. Diethylene triamine (Dow DEH20) is chosen for this cross linking operation. Stoichiometric Ratio of mixing was calculated based on the following equation:

$$Phr \text{ of hardner} = \frac{\text{Hardner eq.wt} \times 100}{\text{Epoxide eq.wt of resin}} \quad (1)$$

where

Phr : parts -by weight- per 100 parts resin.

Eq. wt : weight -in grams- which contains one gram equivalent of material

The final stoichiometric ratio was found to be 10.3:1. This means that for each 10.3 grams of epoxy resin one gram of hardener is mixed to produce a reactive curing resin. Unidirectional strand rovings of E-glass fibers were used as reinforcement. The fiber glass uniweave laminates is used as sheets to be cut in specified mold dimension and used as received. The glass fabric laminate has a surface density of 435 g/m².

Microwave processing system

The system (Fig.1) is made up of a generator, a circulator, a 3-sub-tuner, a directional coupler, a heating cavity and control unit. The main component of the generator is a water-cooled 1.9kW multi mode magnetron with a fixed frequency of 2.45 GHz. Multi mode magnetron is needed to assure homogenous microwave distribution in the cavity. The magnetron is protected against thermal overload by a thermal switch. The output power of the magnetron is proportionally varied from 0 to 100%. It is worth while mentioning that the variable power generator system is conceptually different than the home use generator which works on “time slicing” principle. If it is desired to operate a 1000W generator on 25% of full power, a time slicing magnetron applies the full 1000W for 25% of the time, while a variable one applies only 250W for the desired time duration. This real time control raises the price of the magnetron tremendously. However, the increase in price is reflected in better performance. It is evident that the variable power microwave produces higher reaction rate for epoxy resin than the pulsed power system and at the same time, more control over the cure cycle is achievable [11].

Figure 1: Schematic Diagram of the Microwave Processing system

A fully configurable, high accuracy process controller is used to control the curing process. The controller is supplied from Eurotherm[®]. A maximum of 20 programs can be designed to achieve specific heating profiles. In addition, dedicated software, iTools[®] Version 4, was supplied with the system. The software is a useful utility that enables programming,

monitoring, and recording the process parameters of the heating process. RS232 connection is used to connect the PC to the data acquisition system.

Thermal curing system

The thermal processing system consists of an electric oven with a temperature control gauge. The temperature is manually set to a desired value. The function of the oven controller is then to continuously adjust the delivered power to control the cavity temperature. In addition a data acquisition collects temperature data through 3 thermocouples attached to the oven. The data acquisition system is operated by a LabView[®] program.

Molds and accessories

In order to process epoxy samples and composites using lay-up method, two different molds were designed and manufactured from aluminum and Teflon. The aluminium mold is to be used for oven curing while the Teflon mold is to be used for microwave curing. Teflon is considered the most suitable material for microwave processing due to its low dielectric properties, ϵ'' is around 0.0003. Teflon mold (120X20X4mm) is slightly larger than the aluminium one (80X16X4mm). The main reason is that the microwave thermocouple which is 3 mm thick will be inserted into the side of the Teflon mold. This necessitates a larger width to assure more representative temperature reading. Having both the same thickness, however, will make the mechanical testing data comparable to each other. Both the aluminium and Teflon mold had to be waxed with a release agent. The sides had to be sealed with silicon rubber to prevent leakage.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

A Perkin Elmer differential Scanning Calorimetry DSC-7 was used to monitor the kinetic behavior of the epoxy resin and to develop the curing model. The power compensation principle mentioned previously is applied in order to carefully measure the heat evolved during the cure cycle of the material. When the temperature rises in the sample material due to exothermic reactions of curing, energy is removed from the cell to compensate for the sample energy. The amount of power required to maintain system equilibrium is directly proportional to the thermal changes occurring in the sample. Sealed Aluminium pans are used for both the sample and reference cells. Calibration was performed using indium and Zinc specimen as reference material with known thermal behavior in order to determine the base line of the machine and assure correct heat flow readings

Universal testing machine

The mechanical testing includes measurement of flexural strength and modulus by three-point bend test according to ASTM D790-02. This standard was applied for both neat resin and fiber composites. A calibrated material testing machine MTS was used with the loading noses and supports installed. The support span used for all tests was 16 times the thickness of the samples (tolerance ± 1). For the 4mm standard thickness of our samples the support span is 64 mm. The rate of crosshead motion used was 2.5 mm/min. During load application, simultaneous recording of load versus time was carried out. The specimen is deflected until rupture occurs in the outer surface.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cure analysis of Epoxy resin

During the curing process of this resin, complex chemical & thermal reactions take place. For a resin to achieve the ultimate physical & mechanical properties the nature of these reactions has to be studied and an optimized kinetic model has to be found for each type of resin. The kinetic model is also an effective way to facilitate numerical modeling of the polymerization process, study ageing and degradation mechanisms, and compare the behavior of resin with diverse forms of heat delivery. DSC measurement will provide heating profile for the calibration process of epoxy resin, in addition to provide a reference point for optimization of the cure cycle of epoxy in microwave heating.

Two main kinetic parameters, degree of cure (α) and the rate of cure ($d\alpha/dt$) are measured by DSC. Degree of cure is generally defined as the partial exothermic or total heat generated at time t with respect to the total heat of reaction. In other words, degree of cure represents the maximum extent to which the cross link reaction has reached during polymerization. It is mathematically represented as:

$$\alpha = \frac{\Delta H_t}{\Delta H} \quad (2)$$

Where ΔH_t is the total heat generated at time t and ΔH is the ultimate heat obtained by dynamically scanning the material.

The function now of the kinetic model is to find a relationship between the experimentally obtained degree of cure and the rate of cure taking into consideration the activation energy of the process and the decrease in the amounts of functional groups as conversion progresses. The curing models have been a vital area of development and many researchers have contributed in this field by suggesting kinetic models that vary extensively in applicability, simplicity, and accuracy. More details on different types of models and the use of each category are discussed elsewhere [12]. For our analysis we shall use an autocatalytic model which assumes that the step reaction products are involved in the chain growth reaction of the polymer. The mathematical representation of this model takes the following form:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K(T)\alpha^m(1-\alpha)^n \quad (3)$$

Where m and n are the reaction orders and $K(T)$ is a temperature-dependant reaction rate constant that has an Arrhenius form. Fig.2 shows the normalized isothermal heat flow measured by DSC for the four curing temperatures of study. Normalization is important to cancel out the effect of mass variation on the specimen cure behavior. The isothermal conversion at isothermal cure of 90 °C, 100 °C, 110 °C, and 120 °C was completed after 21.8, 13.1, 8.9, and 4.4 minutes, respectively. We can immediately notice the increase in the rate of the polymerization reaction as the isothermal temperature increases. In addition, when dealing with microwave curing the DSC curing time will provide the starting point for cycle optimization and provide rich data for analysis and comparison.

Figure 2: Normalized Isothermal Heat Flow at 90, 100, 110, and 120 °C

On the other hand, a dynamic scan is also carried out from 30 °C to 200 °C at a rate of 5 °C/min in order to obtain the ultimate heat of polymerization ΔH . This heat of polymerization is usually obtained by dynamic scan to avoid any minor heat loss during isothermal ramp stage. In order to measure the degree of cure as defined from Eq. 2, it is necessary to calculate first the ultimate heat of polymerization ΔH , which was found to be 446.49 J/g.

Fig.3 is then produced by finding the ratio of the progressive isothermal heat of polymerization at a specified temperature, ΔH_t to the ultimate heat of polymerization, ΔH . From this figure we can notice that the degree of cure did not reach 100 %. This is due to incomplete cure at the isothermal temperature resulting from vitrification. At this stage the mobility of the reacting groups are hindered and the cure mechanism changes to be diffusion controlled [13]. The low scanning rate in the dynamic scan, however, detects most of the minor heats even at diffusion stage to represent the ultimate heat of polymerization.

Figure 3: Degree of cure variation with time at 90, 100, 110, and 120 °C Isothermal Temperature

Since the derivative data $d\alpha/dt$ is also generated automatically from DSC tests, the experimental values of α and $d\alpha/dt$ are then processed using the least square method to determine the model parameters of the following equation:

$$\Rightarrow \ln \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \text{const} + m \ln \alpha + n \ln(1 - \alpha) \quad (4)$$

namely m , n , and $K(T)$. Table 1 states the calculated isothermal parameters. The average ($m + n$) value is 2.28 which agrees with values obtained with other epoxy formulations.

Table 1: Estimation of Isothermal Kinetic Model

Temp °C	ΔH (J/g)	Kinetics Parameters				
		m	n	K	A	E_a (KJ/gm)
90	422.15	0.41	1.60	0.83	2.37E+07	51.8
100	410	0.37	1.77	1.27	2.28E+07	
110	413.69	0.48	2.01	3.10	3.59E+07	
120	403.5	0.45	2.02	3.78	2.90E+07	
Mean		0.43	1.85	2.25	2.79E+07	

In order to appreciate the compatibility of the empirical model, both the experimental and calculated rates of cure are plotted for each isothermal temperature in Fig. 4. The figure shows good correlation between the calculated and the experimental data with the maximum rate of cure obtained at about $\alpha = 0.2$, which agrees with the mathematical characteristic of the autocatalytic model. The maximum observed error in the rate of cure between the experimental and modeled data was found to be 4% at 100 °C. Yet, the maximum error values declines at the rest of the curves to reach 2 %.

Figure 4: Summary of Variation of cure rate with respect to degree of cure

Optimization approach

After examining different curing methods and techniques, it was requested to find out the best combination of segment type and cure time to achieve the highest mechanical properties. First, mechanical properties of a standard isothermal cure cycle, recommended by Dow Chemicals, were compared for oven and microwave curing. Afterwards, a testing plan was developed, which consists of 10 groups of samples including neat resin and fiberglass composites. Each group of settings consisted of 5 samples with the same condition. Heating rate as low as 10 °C/min and as high as 200 °C/min was also inspected. Dwell time was modified to include 60, 30, 20, and 13 min which is the minimum time recommended by DSC at 100 °C. Sample preparation was also inspected such as vacuum degassing and room temperature gelation and the effect on the final mechanical properties was analyzed. All the microwave processing was done using the PID control method while thermal curing was carried out using the oven setup. Due to the fact that cure rate is a function of temperature as was explained in the kinetic analysis, the isothermal temperature was set to 100 °C. This was essential to independently study the effect of processing time.

Table 2 shows the behavior of glass fiber/epoxy composites cured by oven and microwave energy at different dwell time. The heating rate was common for all to be 10 °C/min. The data in brackets is for standard deviation of flexural strength (S_{σ}) and modulus (S_E).

Table 2: Mechanical Properties of Glass Fiber/Epoxy Composites cured at 100 °C

Material	Method	Dwell Time (min)	Flexural Strength (MPa)		Flexural Modulus (GPa)	
			σ_F (S_{σ})	A_{σ}	E_F (S_E)	A_E
GF/Epoxy	Oven	60	209.75 (4.19)	3.41	8.33 (0.65)	0.52
	Microwave	60	228.68 (4.21)	3.37	9.07 (0.39)	0.34
		30	226.28 (4.35)	3.49	9.03 (0.48)	0.37

From this figure several remarks can be deduced:

1. For the recommended 60 minutes cure cycle of Dow chemicals, the microwave strength has increased from 209.75 to 228.68 MPa. Same trend observed for modulus to increase from 8.33 to 9.07 GPa. Microwave curing has relatively improved the mechanical properties of the composites. This can be explained as microwave heating is more homogeneous than thermal curing by elimination of thermal runaway and thermal gradient. The alignment of the epoxy chains boosted the system crystallinity. This explanation was interpreted by the work of several researchers such as Zhou et al. [19](2003).
2. Decreasing the dwell time by 50% resulted in the microwave samples maintaining similar mechanical properties. This finding highlights the need to investigate the full microwave capability to reduce curing time.
3. Good reliability was obtained in the data knowing that the average deviation of flexural strength ranges from 3.37-3.49 MPa for flexural strength and from 0.34-0.52 for the flexural modulus.

The dielectric properties of fiber glass composites are dominated by the dielectric loss of the resin rather than the fiber. This is due to the microwave "transparency" of fiber glass. Therefore, efforts were concentrated on optimizing the cure behavior of the epoxy resin itself. Table 3 shows the mechanical properties of epoxy resin. Different ramp rates and dwell time have been tested. A standard oven cycle was tested against 5 different combinations of microwave cycle.

Table 3: Mechanical Properties of Epoxy Resin cured at 100 °C

Material	Method	Ramp Rate (°C/min)	Dwell Time (min)	Flexural Strength (MPa)		Flexural Modulus (GPa)	
				$\sigma_F S_\sigma$	A_σ	$E_F (S_E)$	A_E
Epoxy Resin	Oven	10	60	71.03 (1.2)	0.92	1.98 (0.14)	0.10
	Microwave	10	30	74.54 (2.21)	1.47	2.17 (0.2)	0.16
		10	20	76.6 (2.4)	1.86	2.01 (0.16)	0.12
		10	13	75.4 (3.1)	2.40	2.08 (0.37)	0.26

The following remarks were deduced:

1. Again as it can be seen, that the flexural strength and modulus for microwave curing have exceeded the values in oven curing. Same explanation as fiber reinforced composites is applicable here.
2. For microwave curing at 10 °C/min heating rate and dwell time were varied from 13-30 minutes, we can see no sharp changes in strength or modulus. This highly supported the credibility of DSC testing. Back to degree of cure chart, figure 5.3, at 100 °C epoxy reaches maximum degree of cure at 13 minutes.

CONCLUSION

A common remark observed in all the past work is the lack of optimization approach of the problem. The use of power setting, curing temperature, and processing time were randomly selected in most of the time. Therefore, a more intelligent approach was introduced by fixing some process variable such as cure temperature and utilization of efficient process control. Time durations were also varied based on DSC kinetic analysis to find out the maximum time reduction at the highest possible degree of cure. A fully reliable kinetic model was found to describe the material behavior which will provide a major amount of information for future work. Gelation time was evaluated and found to be effective in providing high property composites. The increase of flexural strength and modulus in the case of microwave curing has agreed with previous results stating that using microwave processing, higher cure uniformity, higher mechanical properties, and enhanced cure kinetics are expected.

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